

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8052775>
УДК 567.31

FOSSIL SHARKS FROM ALBIAN AND CENOMANIAN DEPOSITS OF THE KURSK OBLAST (RUSSIA)

S.V. Solonin,

Research assistant,
Ryazan State University named for S. Yesenin,
Ryazan

V.V. Koroy,

Independent researcher,
Kursk

D.V. Portnyagin,

Master student,
Kursk State University,
Kursk

Annotation: This article briefly describes fossil selachian assemblages from the Albian-Cenomanian ages from three localities in Kursk Oblast. The collected material is mainly represented by isolated shark teeth. A total of 14 unambiguous taxa have been identified including cf. *Polyacrodus* sp., *Notidanodon* sp., *Heterodontus* sp., *Cederstroemia* sp., cf. *Pseudomegachasma* sp., *Archaeolamna* ex.gr. *kopingensis*, *Dwardius* sp., *Cretoxyrhina* cf. *C. vraconensis*, *Paraisurus macrorhiza*, *Squalicorax* sp., *Protolamna* sp., *Eostriatolamia* sp., *Synechodus* sp., and *Paraorthacodus* sp. These taxa are all new to the Cretaceous selachian fossil record of Kursk Oblast. These fossil materials allow for improvements in our knowledge in the paleoecology and species-richness of East-European, Albian-Cenomanian selachian assemblages. Further study of selachian material from Cretaceous deposits in Kursk Oblast may further clarify information on the geographical distribution, paleobiogeography, paleoecology and taxonomic diversity of this group of vertebrates, both in the Early Cretaceous and Late Cretaceous in Central Russia, and in Europe as a whole.

Keywords: Kursk Oblast, elasmobranchii, selachians, Cenomanian, Albian

ИСКОПАЕМЫЕ АКУЛЫ ИЗ АЛЬБСКИХ И СЕНОМАНСКИХ ОТЛОЖЕНИЙ КУРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ (РОССИЯ)

С.В. Солонин,

нс,

Рязанский государственный университет имени С.А. Есенина,

г. Рязань

В.В. Корой,

независимый исследователь,

г. Курск

Д.В. Портнягин,

магистрант,

Курский государственный университет,

г. Курск

Аннотация: В данной статье кратко описаны ископаемые комплексы селяхий альб-сеноманского возраста из трех местонахождений Курской области. Собранный материал преимущественно представлен изолированными зубами акул. В общей сложности было идентифицировано 14 однозначных таксонов, включая cf. *Polyacrodus* sp., *Notidanodon* sp., *Heterodontus* sp., *Cederstroemia* sp., cf. *Pseudomegachasma* sp., *Archaeolamna* ex.gr. *kopingensis*, *Dwardius* sp., *Cretoxyrhina* cf. *C. vracconensis*, *Paraisurus macrorhiza*, *Squalicorax* sp., *Protolamna* sp., *Eostriatolamia* sp., *Synechodus* sp., *Paraorthacodus* sp. Все вышеперчисленные таксоны впервые отмечены в летописи меловых селяхий Курской области. Изученный ископаемый материал позволяет расширить наши знания в области палеоэкологии и видового разнообразия восточноевропейских альб-сеноманских сообществ селяхий. Дальнейшие исследования материала селяхий из меловых отложений Курской области могут дополнительно уточнить данные по географическому распространению, палеогеографии, палеоэкологии и таксономическому разнообразию данной группы позвоночных, как в раннемеловое, так и в позднемеловое время в Центральной России и Европе в целом.

Ключевые слова: Курская область, эласмобранхии, селяхии, сеноман, альб

Introduction. Cretaceous deposits are widespread in Kursk Oblast, of the Russian Federation, and are represented by rocks of both the Lower and Upper Cretaceous. In Kursk's exposures of these rocks, all stages of this system are represented. The Berriasian - Valanginian deposits are represented by sands and siltstones, Hauterivian - Barremian, by siltstone clays with inclusions of sands, Aptian, by sands, siltstones and clays, and Albian, by siltstone sands. Upper Cretaceous deposits overlie rocks of Lower Cretaceous age. Cenomanian deposits are represented by greenish-gray, quartz-glaucanite sands containing several horizons of phosphorites and sandy chalk; Turonian, by sandy chalk and chalk, Coniacian, by chalk and chalk-like marls, Santonian, by micaceous marls, Campanian, by chalk and siltstone, and Maastrichtian by white chalk [1, 2].

In the Kursk Oblast, Cretaceous sediments, based on the analyzed data, were formed both in coastal shallow water (during the Berriasian-Cenomanian) and in deeper water (for most of the Turonian-Maastrichtian) conditions [3-5].

Cretaceous shark assemblages of the central part of European Russia have been studied rather incompletely. From the Lower Cretaceous, there are no documented reports on elasmobranch fossils at all. In general, Early Cretaceous (especially pre-Albian) selachian assemblages have been studied rather poorly globally as well [6; 7]. The history of the study of Cretaceous (Late Cretaceous) sharks in central Russia began with studies in the Kursk and neighboring Oryol oblasts and goes back to the middle of the 19th century. Then the Russian paleontologist, engineer and geologist Valerian Kiprijanoff from the Cenomanian-age phosphorite deposits of the Kursk and Orel oblast, named by him "Siwerischen Osteolith" or "Kursk samorod", on the area between the cities of Kursk and Orel, along the highway then under construction between these cities, was collected and in several papers described the material of fossil selachian, presented by the following taxa: *Ptychodus decurrens*, *P. latissimus*, *P. polygyrus*, *P. mammillaris*, *P. oweni*, *Hybodus* sp., *Carcharias medius*, *Corax heterodon*, *Otodus brandti*, *Otodus crassus*, *Otodus renardi*, *Otodus basalis*, *Otodus subbasalis*, *Oxyrhina rouillieri*, *Lamna raphiodon*, *Lamna subulata*, *Squatina moelleri*.

At the same time, at least *Ptychodus latissimus*, *P. polygyrus*, *Hybodus* sp., *Corax heterodon*, *Otodus crassus*, *Otodus renardi*, *Otodus basalis*, *Otodus subbasalis*, *Lamna subulata* were described from Kursk Oblast [8-12]. Of course, the material described from in the 19th century is in need of revision, as well as clarification of the geography of the finds. By the end of the 19th century, there are reports on the findings of shark teeth in Cenomanian layers from Lyaminsky ravine near the Yakhroma City (Moscow Oblast), where the recovered shark fossils belonged to species such as *Eostriatolamia subulata*, *Cretalamna appendiculata*, *Ptychodu spolygyrus*, *P. mammillaris* [13]. Already at the beginning of this century, shark teeth belonging to *Palaeoanacorax volgensis*, *Synechodus dispar*, *Paraorthacodus recurvus*, *Scapanorhynchus* cf. *raphiodon*, *Pseudoisurus macrorhizus*, *P. lomosus* and *Squatina muelleri* were additionally identified from this region. In the same-aged sediments of the Varavinsky ravine, near the village of Varavino (Moscow Oblast). The presence of *Synechodus dispar*, *Eostriatolamia subulata*, *Scapanorhynchus raphiodon*, *Pseudoisurus tomosus*, *Pseudoisurus macrorhizus*, *Ptychodus* sp. can additionally be established [14]. A few other fossil shark finds were noted from the Bryansk and Tambov oblasts [6, 15]. Thus, in the vicinity of the city of Bryansk, the presence of *Palaeoanacorax volgensis* was also noted from Cenomanian deposits [6].

Recently, the presence of at least 35 elasmobranchs taxa, including 8 species of *Ptychodus*, was established in the Upper Cretaceous deposits near the Shatsk City, Ryazan Oblast [16-19].

In general, the Cretaceous selachians of European Russia are most fully studied in the Volga region, where a diverse elasmobranchs material from several Late Cretaceous localities of the Penza, Volgograd, Saratov oblasts is reported [20-24]. In addition, in 2022, a complex of Late Cretaceous fish, including twelve elasmobranch taxa, was described for the first time in Russia from the Campanian deposits of the Saratov Oblast [25, 26].

Materials and methods. All the material documented here was collected from the fossiliferous layers of three localities of the Kursk Oblast, described below. This collection consists of 309 specimens in total, represented mainly by poorly preserved shark teeth and fragments of them - 308 specimens, as well as 1 shark's fin spine. Only 52

specimens are identifiable at least up to the genus level. Of these, six are from the Kamyshinsky ravine locality (Kursk District), 27 from the Krivtsovskaya beam locality (Shchigrovsky District), and are 19 from the Rzhavoplotovskaya beam locality (Zolotukhinsky District). All specimens are housed in the collections of the Geological Museum of Kursk State University and the Kurchatov Museum of Local Lore.

The material reported herein was obtained by bulk sampling and subsequent screen washing of sediments with the use of sieves with a mesh size of 1.5 mm. Specimens were photographed using a Canon EOS 2000D camera with an 18-200 mm Tamron lens. The drawings were prepared using GIMP (v. 2.8.16).

Localities and assemblages overview.

The first locality described here is the Kamyshinsky ravine, located on the right bank of the Vinogrobl River, in its valley, near the village of Kamyshi (Kursk District) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Geographical map showing the location of the localities with fossil shark assemblages in the Kursk Oblast. Kamyshinsky ravine locality (1), Krivtsovskaya beam locality (2), Rzhavoplotovskaya beam locality (3)

It is an elongated ravine 30 meters from east to west, turning into a beam, having a steep slope in its central part (angle of inclination

up to 90 degrees) the side, the height of which from the base reaches 7 meters. According to the geological map of the pre-Quaternary deposits of the Kursk Oblast, Albian deposits lie here under the Quaternary rocks [1].

The total thickness of the Cretaceous deposits reaches 6 meters. These deposits consist of quartz-glaucinite sand with an admixture of limonite with layers of phosphorites and sandstones. The section clearly shows 2 layers of quartz sand with phosphorite pebbles at a depth of about 0.6 meters and 4 meters from the surface.

The fossil selachian material was collected from the second phosphorite layer from the surface. Unfortunately, no detailed geological and stratigraphic studies have been conducted here and no stratigraphically important taxa have been previously reported. However, the age of the selachian assemblage is no older than Albian. Thus, based on the data of the geological map of the pre-Quaternary deposits of the Kursk Oblast as well as the taxonomic composition of the sharks, this layer, apparently has an Albian age [1].

It has been established that the shark assemblage here is represented by the following taxa: cf. *Polyacrodus* sp., *Cederstroemia* sp., *Archaeolamna* ex.gr. *kopingensis*, *Dwardius* sp., and *Cretoxyrhina* cf. *C. vracconensis* (Fig. 2). This assemblage belongs to three orders – Hybodontiformes, Orectolobiformes and Lamniformes and 4 families – Orectolobidae, Archaeolamnidae, Cardabiodontidae and Cretoxyrhinidae.

Figure 2 – Shark teeth from the Kamyshinsky ravine locality in the Kursk Oblast. *Archaeolamna* ex.gr. *kopingensis*, tooth (A-AI): lingual view (A), labial view (AI); *Cretoxyrhina* cf. *C. vraconensis*, tooth (B-BI): lingual view (B), labial view (BI); *Eostriatolamia* sp., tooth (C-CI): lingual view (C), labial view (CI); *Cederstroemia* sp., tooth (D-DII): lingual view (D), labial view (DI), apical view (DII); cf. *Polyacrodus* sp., tooth (E-EII): occlusal view (E), labial view (EI), lingual view (EII); *Dwardius* sp., tooth (F-FI): lingual view (F), labial view (FI). All scale bars represent 1 cm.

In addition, elements of chimaeras dental plates and fragments of crowns of marine reptile's teeth were collected here.

The second described locality is the Krivtsovskaya beam, located near the village of Krivtsovka (Shchigrovsky District), about 10 km northwest of the town of Shchigry, on the left bank of the Tuskar River (Fig. 1). This locality is a small beam, sometimes complicated by washouts, the thickness of the deposits of which reaches 8.5 meters from the base.

According to the geological map of the pre-Quaternary deposits of the Kursk Oblast, deposits of the Albian age here lie under rocks of Quaternary age [1].

The Cretaceous deposits exposed here mainly consist of quartz-glaucinite sand with layers of phosphorites and sandstones at the base, as well as brown clay and marl with an admixture of writing chalk in the upper part of the section. Seven layers can be clearly traced in the wall of the beam under the soil cover, including two layers with phosphorite pebbles and a layer with large sandstone bodies.

The studied material of the described locality was collected from a layer of coarse-grained quartz sand with inclusions of large sandstone bodies, about three meters from the surface. Detailed geological and stratigraphic studies have also not been carried out here, and no stratigraphically important invertebrate taxa have been previously identified. However, based on the composition of the marine vertebrate's complex, including sharks, as well as data from the geological map of the pre-Quaternary deposits of the Kursk Oblast, this layer probably has an Albian age [8].

It has been established that the shark assemblage here is represented by the following taxa: cf. *Polyacrodus* sp., *Notidanodon* sp., *Cederstroemia* sp., *Archaeolamna* ex.gr. *kopingensis*, *Cretoxyrhina* cf. *C. vracensis*, *Paraisurus macrorhiza*, *Squalicorax* sp., *Protolamna* sp., *Eostriatolamia* sp., and *Synechodus* sp. (Fig.3). This assemblage belongs to five orders – Hybodontiformes, Hexanchiformes, Orectolobiformes, Lamniformes, Synechodontiformes and 8 families – Hexanchidae, Orectolobidae, Archaeolamnidae, Cretoxyrhinidae, Paraisuridae, Anacoracidae, Pseudoscapanorhynchidae, and Palaeospinacidae.

Figure 3 – Shark teeth from the Krivtsovskaya beam locality in the Kursk Oblast. *Archaeolamna* ex.gr. *kopingensis*, teeth (A-BI): lingual view (A,B), labial view (AI,BI); *Protolamna* sp., tooth: lingual view (C), labial view (CI); *Cretoxyrhina* cf. *C. vraconensis*, tooth: lingual view (D), labial view (DI); *Paraisurus macrorrhiza*, tooth (E-EII): lingual view (E), labial view (EI), lateral view (EII); *Squalicorax* sp., teeth (F-GI): lingual view (F,G), labial view (FI,GI); cf. *Polyacrodus* sp., tooth (H-HI): lingual view (H), occlusal view (HI) *Cederstroemia* sp., tooth (I-II): lingual view (I), labial view (II); *Synechodus* sp., teeth (J-KI): lingual view (J,K), labial view (JI,KI); *Eostriatolamia* sp., tooth (L-LI): (A-BI): lingual view (L), labial view (LI); *Notidanodon* sp., tooth (M-MI): lingual view (M), labial view (MI). All scale bars represent 1 cm

Separately, it is worth noting a tooth attributed to the genus *Notidanodon*, the remains of which are very rare in the fossil record in Russia, was recovered from this locality [27].

In addition, the crowns of bony fish teeth (cf. *Protosphyraena* sp., Crossognathiformes indet.) are collected here; elements of the dental plates of chimeras, bone fragments and tooth crowns of marine reptiles (plesiosaurs and ichthyosaurs) are less common.

The third described locality is the Rzhavoplotovskaya beam, located near the village of Rzhavaya Plota (Zolotukhinsky District), on the right bank of the Rzhanets River (Fig.1). It is a beam stretched from north to south for more than 100 meters, having a steep (angle of inclination up to 90 degrees) eastern wall, the height of which reaches 15 meters. In the northern part of the beam, a landslide complicates it. According to the geological map of the pre-Quaternary deposits of the Kursk Oblast, the deposits of Cenomanian-Turonian age lies here under the rocks of the Quaternary age [1].

The Cretaceous deposits exposed here mainly consists of quartz-glaucinite sand with an admixture of limonite with layers of phosphorites and sandstones, in the upper part with an admixture of siltstone. The section clearly shows two layers of quartz sand with phosphorite pebbles at a depth of about 1.7 meters and 4.7 meters from the surface.

The fossil material of the described locality was collected from the second from the surface phosphorite layer. The age of this layer is apparently Cenomanian, based on the selachian taxa typical of the Cenomanian. In addition, the layer lies at the level of Cenomanian sediments in the valley of the Rzhanets River in the immediate vicinity of the described location [1].

Here was established the selachian remains belong to cf. *Polyacrodus* sp., *Heterodontus* sp., cf. *Pseudomegachasma* sp., *Archaeolamna* ex.gr. kopingensis, *Dwardius* sp., *Squalicorax* sp., *Eostriatolamia* sp., *Synechodus* sp., and *Paraorthacodus* sp. (Fig.4). This assemblage belongs to five orders - Hybodontiformes, Heterodontiformes, Orectolobiformes, Lamniformes, and Synechodontiformes and 7 families - Heterodontidae, Odontaspidae, Archaeolamnidae, Cardabiodontidae, Anacoracidae, Pseudoscapanorhynchidae, and Palaeospinacidae.

Figure 4 – Selachian remains from the Rzhavoplotovskaya beam locality in the Kursk Oblast. *Archaeolamna* ex.gr. *kopingensis*, teeth (A-BI): lingual view (A,B), labial view (AI,BI); *Pseudomegachasma* sp., tooth (C-CII): lingual view (C), labial view (CI), lateral view (CII); *Eostriatolamia* sp., tooth (D-DI): lingual view (D), labial view (DI); *Dwardius* sp., tooth (E-EI): lingual view (E), labial view (EI); *Squalicorax* sp., tooth (F-FI): lingual view (F), labial view (FI); *Paraorthacodus* sp., tooth (G-GI): lingual view (G), labial view (GI); *Synechodus* sp., tooth (H-HI): lingual view (H), labial view (HI); cf. *Polyacrodus* sp., tooth (I-II): occlusal view (I), labial view (II); *Heterodontus* sp., dorsal fin spine (J): lateral view. All scale bars represent 1 cm.

The crowns of bony fish teeth (*Protosphyraena* sp., Pycnodontiformes indet.), elements of chimaeras dental plates, bone fragments and crowns of marine reptile’s teeth, as well as numerous fragments of petrified wood were also collected in the fossiliferous layer.

Conclusions. In this paper, three new localities with fossil shark assemblages in the Kursk Oblast were briefly described. Two selachian assemblages have an Albian age (assemblages from the Kamyshinsky ravine and the Krittsovskaya beam), one assemblage has a Cenomanian age (assemblage from the Rzhavoplotovskaya beam).

In total, out of the three localities described above, the presence of at least 14 unambiguous taxa was established (cf. *Polyacrodus* sp., *Notidanodon* sp., *Heterodontus* sp., *Cederstroemia* sp., cf. *Pseudomegachasma* sp., *Archaeolamna* ex.gr. *kopingensis*, *Dwardius* sp., *Cretoxyrhina* cf. *C. vraconensis*, *Paraisurus macrorhiza*, *Squalicorax* sp., *Protolamna* sp., *Eostriatolamia* sp., *Synechodus* sp., and *Paraorthacodus* sp.).

The most diverse selachian assemblage was established in the Albian deposits of the Krittsovskaya beam with 10 taxa, as well as in the Cenomanian deposits of the Rzhavoplotovskaya beam - 9 taxa. The shark assemblage from the Albian deposits of the Kamyshinsky ravine is less diverse (6 taxa), apparently due to the small number of material collected from here, in comparison with the other two aforementioned localities. The comparative taxonomic composition of the assemblages from the studied localities is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Comparative taxonomic composition of the selachian assemblages of the studied localities

Taxa	Kamyshinsky ravine	Krittsovskaya beam	Rzhavoplotovskaya beam
cf. <i>Polyacrodus</i> sp.	+	+	+
<i>Notidanodon</i> sp.		+	
<i>Heterodontus</i> sp.			+
<i>Cederstroemia</i> sp.	+	+	
cf. <i>Pseudomegachasma</i> sp.			+
<i>Archaeolamna</i>	+	+	+

Taxa	Kamyshinsky ravine	Krivtsovskaya beam	Rzhavoplotovskaya beam
ex.gr. <i>kopingensis</i>			
<i>Dwardius</i> sp.	+		+
<i>Cretoxyrhina</i> cf. <i>C. vracconensis</i>	+	+	
<i>Paraisurus</i> <i>macrorhiza</i>		+	
<i>Squalicorax</i> sp.		+	+
<i>Protolamna</i> sp.		+	
<i>Eostriatolamia</i> sp.	+	+	+
<i>Synechodus</i> sp.		+	+
<i>Paraorthacodus</i> sp.			+

The basis of sharks taxonomic diversity consists of the order Lamniformes (8 taxa), there are also representatives of the order Synechodontiformes (2 taxa), Hybodontiformes (1 taxon), Orectolobiformes (1 taxon), Heterodontiformes (1 taxon), and Hexanchiformes (1 taxon).

It is worth noting the representative of the Hexanchiformes order – the genus *Notidanodon*, whose remains are extremely rare in the fossil record on the territory of Russia [27]. Most of the collected specimens cannot be identified to the species level, due to their small number, fragmentary nature, as well as poor preservation of the available material. At the same time, a number of genera present here, such as *Squalicorax* and *Synechodus*, can be represented by more than one species.

This study attempts a preliminary description of new Cretaceous selachian assemblages from the Kursk Oblast. This allowed us to somewhat improve our knowledge of the Albian-Cenomanian shark assemblages of the Eastern European region. These taxa are new to the Cretaceous selachian fossil record of Kursk Oblast. At the same time, the Albian selachian assemblages are of particular interest, due to their poor study in Russia.

Further study of selachian material from Cretaceous deposits of the Kursk Oblast will clarify the data on the geographical distribution, paleoecology and taxonomic diversity of this vertebrates group, both in the

Early Cretaceous and Late Cretaceous in Central Russia and Europe as a whole.

Acknowledgements. We deeply thanks to Ryan Shell (Department of Vertebrate Paleontology, Cincinnati Museum Center, USA) for improving the English and for the constructive suggestions that we hope have improved the manuscript. The authors also express their gratitude to all those who took part in the excavations and collected fossil material.

Bibliography

[1] Geological map of pre-Quaternary deposits of the Kursk region. Scale 1:500,000 [Map] / ch. ed. N.I. Sychkin - Moscow: Ministry of Natural Resources of the Russian Federation Central Regional Geological Center, 1998.

[2] Geology of the USSR. Voronezh and adjacent regions. Part 1. Geological description [Text] / ch. ed. I.I. Malyshev - Moscow: State publishing house of geological literature, 1949. 348 p. T.6.

[3] State Geological Map of the Russian Federation. Scale 1:1,000,000 (third generation). Series Central European. Sheet M-37 - Voronezh. Explanatory note [Text] / A. M. Akhmedov, N. K. Klyuev, A. N. Naumkin et al. - St. Petersburg: VSEGEI Cartographic Factory, 2011. 255 p.

[4] Paleogeography of the USSR. Explanatory note to the Atlas of Lithological and Paleogeographic Maps of the USSR [Text] / ch. ed. A.P. Vinogradov - Moscow: Nedra publishing house, 1975. 200 p. T.3.

[5] State Geological Map of the Russian Federation. Scale 1:1,000,000 (third generation). Series Central European. Sheet N-36 (M 36) - Smolensk. Explanatory note [Text] / G. V. Vоротnikova, E. A. Gavryushova, S. V. Drutskoy and others - St. Petersburg: Cartographic factory VSEGEI, 2011. 267 p.

[6] Glikman L.S. Evolution of the Cretaceous and Cenozoic lamnoid sharks [Text] / L.S. Glikman - Moscow: Nauka Publishing House, 1980. 248 p.

[7] Sokolskyi T. Elasmobranch (Chondrichthyes) assemblages from the Albian (Lower Cretaceous) of Ukraine [Text] / T. Sokolskyi, G. Guinot // Cretaceous Research. - 2021. No. 117. 104603 p. DOI 10.1016/j.cretres.2020.104603.

[8] Kiprijanoff V. Fisch-Ueberreste im Kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine (nugget) [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. - 1852. No. 25(4). 483-495 p.

[9] Kiprijanoff V. Fisch-Ueberreste im Kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine (nugget) [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. - 1853a. No. 26. 286-294 p.

[10] Kiprijanoff V. Fisch-Ueberreste im Kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine (nugget) [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. - 1853b. No. 26(2). 331-336 p.

[11] Kiprijanoff V. Fisch-Ueberreste im Kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine (nugget) [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. - 1854. No. 27(4). 373-397 p.

[12] Kiprijanoff V. Fish-Ueberreste im kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine oder Siwerischen Osteolith [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. - 1881. No. 55(4). 1-30p.

[13] Nikitin S.N. Traces of the Cretaceous period in Central Russia [Text] / S.N. Nikitin - St. Petersburg: Proceedings of the Geological Committee, 1888. 163 p.

[14] Olferyev A.G. Stratigraphic scheme of the Upper Cretaceous deposits of the East European Platform: Explanatory note [Text] / A.G. Olferyev, A.S. Alekseev - Moscow: Paleontological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2005. 204 p.

[15] Eremin A.V. Geology of the Tambov region. Part 1. Precambrian. Paleozoic. Mesozoic / A.V. Eremin - Tambov: TSU Publishing House. G.R. Derzhavina, 1998. 112 p. T.1.

[16] Vodorezov A.V. The unique location of the teeth of fossil sharks in the vicinity of the village of Maly Prolom (Shatsky district, Ryazan region) in the light of the prospects for creating a natural monument of regional significance / A.V. Vodorezov, S.V. Solonin [Text] // Geographic and geocological research in solving regional environmental problems: materials of the All-Russian Scientific and Practical Conference - Ryazan: S. A. Yesenin Russian State University, 2017. 138-144 p.

[17] Prospects for the creation and practical use of new specially protected natural areas of geological and geomorphological profile in the territory of the Ryazan region [Text] / V.A. Krivtsov, A.V. Vodorezov, S.V. Solonin, S.A. Tobratov // Bulletin of the Ryazan State University named after S. A. Yesenin. - 2018. No. 3 (60). 108-119 p.

[18] Solonin S., Shell R., Vodorezov A., Niedźwiedzki R. Preliminary report of an Upper Cretaceous elasmobranch fauna from Ryazan Oblast, Russia // Geological Society of America Abstracts with Programs. –2020. 6 p. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25182.46404.

[19] The extinct shark, *Ptychodus* (Elasmobranchii, Ptychodontidae) in the Upper Cretaceous of central-western Russia – The road to the easternmost peri-Tethyan seas [Text] / M. Amadori, S.V. Solonin, A.V. Vodorezov et al. // Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology. – 2022. No. 42 (2). e2162909. DOI: 10.1080/02724634.2022.2162909.

[20] Biryukov A.V. On the stratigraphic significance of elasmobranchs (Chondrichthyes, Elasmobranchii) in the Cenomanian of the Right Bank of the Volga region [Text] / A.V. Biryukov // Proceedings of the Saratov University. New episode. Earth Science Series. - 2018. No. 18 (1). 27-40 s.

[21] Glikman L.S. Upper Cretaceous vertebrates of the vicinity of Saratov. Preliminary data [Text] / L.S. Glikman // Scientific notes of the Saratov University. - 1953. No. 38. 51-54 p.

[22] Sintsov I.F. Jurassic and Cretaceous fossils of Saratov Province [Text] / I.F. Sintsov – Spb.: Tipografiya Imperatorskoj Akademii nauk, 1872. – 127 p.

[23] Popov E.V. An Annotated Bibliography of the Soviet Palaeoichthyologist Leonid Glickman (1929–2000) [Text] / E.V. Popov // Proceedings of the Zoological Institute RAS. – 2016. – № 320 (1) P. 25-49.

[24] Sinzow J. Notizen uber die Jura-Kreide-und Neogen-Ablagerung der Gouvernements Saratow, Simbirsk, Samara und Orenburg [Text] / J. Sinzow Odessa: Ekonomische Buch-u. Steindruckerei, 1899 112 c.

[25] Solonin S.V. New data on the Campanian ichthyofauna of the Lower Volga region [Text]/ C.B. Солонин, М.С. Архангельский // Priroda. – 2022. – № 3(1279). – P. 57-59. DOI: 10.7868/S0032874X2203005X.

[26] Marine Fishes (Chondrichthyes, Holocephali, Actinopterygii) from the Upper Cretaceous (Campanian) Rybushka Formation near Beloe Ozero, Saratov Oblast, Russia [Text] / J.A. Ebersole, S.V. Solonin, D.J. Cicimurri et al.// Rivista Italiana di Paleontologia e Stratigrafia. – 2022. – № 128(2). – P. 369–409. DOI: 10.54103/2039-4942/16954.

[27] Trikolidi F.A. Cow sharks (Hexanchiformes) from Cretaceous deposits of the Crimea [Text] / F.A. Trikolidi // Trudy Zoologicheskogo instituta RAN. – 2014. –318(1) – P. 76–97.

Список литературы (перевод)

[1] Геологическая карта дочетвертичных отложений Курской области. Масштаб 1:500 000 [Карта] / гл. ред. Н.И. Сычкин – Москва: МПР РФ Центральный региональный геологический центр, 1998.

[2] Геология СССР. Воронежская и смежные области. Часть 1. Геологическое описание [Текст] / гл. ред. И.И. Малышев – Москва: Государственное издательство геологической литературы, 1949. 348 с. Т.6.

[3] Государственная геологическая карта Российской Федерации. Масштаб 1:1 000 000 (третье поколение). Серия Центрально-Европейская. Лист М-37 – Воронеж. Объяснительная записка [Текст] / А. М. Ахмедов, Н. К. Клюев, А. Н. Наумкин и др. – Санкт-Петербург: Картографическая фабрика ВСЕГЕИ, 2011. 255 с.

[4] Палеогеография СССР. Объяснительная записка к Атласу литолого-палеогеографических карт СССР [Текст] / гл. ред. А.П. Виноградов – Москва: издательство «Недра», 1975. 200 с. Т.3.

[5] Государственная геологическая карта Российской Федерации. Масштаб 1:1 000 000 (третье поколение). Серия Центрально-Европейская. Лист N-36 (М 36) – Смоленск. Объяснительная записка [Текст] / Г. В. Воротникова, Е. А. Гаврюшова, С. В. Друцкой и др. – СПб.: Картографическая фабрика ВСЕГЕИ, 2011. 267 с.

[6] Гликман Л.С. Эволюция меловых и кайнозойских ламноидных акул [Текст] / Л.С. Гликман – Москва: издательство «Наука», 1980. 248 с.

[7] Sokolskyi T. Elasmobranch (Chondrichthyes) assemblages from the Albian (Lower Cretaceous) of Ukraine [Text] / T. Sokolskyi, G. Guinot // Cretaceous Research. – 2021. № 117. 104603 p. DOI 10.1016/j.cretres.2020.104603.

[8] Kiprijanoff V. Fisch-Ueberreste im Kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine (самородъ) [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. – 1852. № 25(4). 483-495 p.

[9] Kiprijanoff V. Fisch-Ueberreste im Kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine (самородъ) [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. – 1853a. № 26. 286-294 p.

[10] Kiprijanoff V. Fisch-Ueberreste im Kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine (самородъ) [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. – 1853b. № 26(2). 331-336 p.

[11] Kiprijanoff V. Fisch-Ueberreste im Kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine (самородъ) [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. – 1854. № 27(4). 373-397 p.

[12] Kiprijanoff V. Fish-Ueberreste im kurskischen eisenhaltigen Sandsteine oder Siwerischen Osteolith [Text] / V. Kiprijanoff // Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. – 1881. № 55(4). 1-30 p.

[13] Никитин С.Н. Следы мелового периода в Центральной России [Текст] / С.Н. Никитин – Спб.: Труды геологического комитета, 1888. 163 с.

[14] Олферьев А.Г. Стратиграфическая схема верхнемеловых отложений Восточно-Европейской платформы: Объяснительная записка [Текст] / А.Г. Олферьев, А.С. Алексеев – Москва: Палеонтологический институт РАН, 2005. 204 с.

[15] Еремин А.В. Геология Тамбовской области. Часть 1. Докембрий. Палеозой. Мезозой / А.В. Еремин – Тамбов: издательство ТГУ им. Г.Р. Державина, 1998. 112 с. Т.1.

[16] Водорезов А.В. Уникальное местонахождение зубов ископаемых акул в окрестностях села Малый Пролом (Шацкий район, Рязанская область) в свете перспектив создания памятника природы регионального значения / А.В. Водорезов, С.В. Солонин [Текст] // Географические и геоэкологические исследования в решении региональных экологических проблем: материалы Всероссийской научно-практической конференции – Рязань: РГУ имени С. А. Есенина, 2017. 138-144 с.

[17] Перспективы создания и возможности практического использования новых особо охраняемых природных территорий геолого-геоморфологического профиля на территории Рязанской области [Текст] / В.А. Кривцов, А.В. Водорезов, С.В. Солонин, С.А. Тобратов // Вестник Рязанского государственного университета имени С. А. Есенина. – 2018. № 3 (60). 108-119 с.

[18] Solonin S., Shell R., Vodorezov A., Niedźwiedzki R. Preliminary report of an Upper Cretaceous elasmobranch fauna from Ryazan Oblast, Russia // Geological Society of America Abstracts with Programs. –2020. 6 p. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25182.46404.

[19] The extinct shark, *Ptychodus* (Elasmobranchii, Ptychodontidae) in the Upper Cretaceous of central-western Russia – The road to easternmost peri-Tethyan seas [Text] / M. Amadori, S.V. Solonin, A.V. Vodorezov et al. // *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*. – 2022. № 42 (2). e2162909. DOI: 10.1080/02724634.2022.2162909.

[20] Бирюков А.В. О стратиграфическом значении эласмобранхий (*Chondrichthyes*, *Elasmobranchii*) в сеномане Правобережного Поволжья [Текст] / А.В. Бирюков // *Известия Саратовского университета. Новая серия. Серия Науки о Земле*. – 2018. № 18 (1). 27-40 с.

[21] Гликман Л.С. Верхнемеловые позвоночные окрестностей Саратова. Предварительные данные [Текст] / Л.С. Гликман // *Ученые записки Саратовского университета*. – 1953. № 38. 51-54 с.

[22] Синцов И.Ф. Об юрских и меловых ископаемых Саратовской губернии [Текст] / И.Ф. Синцов – Спб.: Типография Императорской Академии наук, 1872. 127 с.

[23] Popov E.V. An Annotated Bibliography of the Soviet Palaeoichthyologist Leonid Glickman (1929–2000) [Text] / E.V. Popov // *Proceedings of the Zoological Institute RAS*. – 2016. № 320 (1) 25-49 p.

[24] [Sinzow J. Notizen uber die Jura-Kreide-und Neogen-Ablagerung der Gouvernements Saratow, Simbirsk, Samara und Orenburg [Text] / J. Sinzow – Odessa: “*Ekonomische*” Buch-u. Steindruckerei, 1899. 112 с.

[25] Солонин С.В. Новые данные о кампанской ихтиофауне Нижнего Поволжья [Текст] / С.В. Солонин, М.С. Архангельский // *Природа*. – 2022. № 3(1279). 57-59 с. DOI: 10.7868/S0032874X2203005X.

[26] Marine Fishes (*Chondrichthyes*, *Holocephali*, *Actinopterygii*) from the Upper Cretaceous (Campanian) Rybushka Formation near Beloe Ozero, Saratov Oblast, Russia [Text] / J.A. Ebersole, S.V. Solonin, D.J. Cicimurri et al. // *Rivista Italiana di Paleontologia e Stratigrafia*. – 2022. № 128(2). 369-409 с. DOI: 10.54103/2039-4942/16954.

[27] Триколиди Ф.А. Гребнезубые акулы (*Hexanchiformes*) из меловых отложений Крыма [Текст] / Ф.А. Триколиди // *Труды Зоологического института РАН*. – 2014. №318(1) 76-97 с.

© S.V. Solonin, V.V. Koroy, D.V. Portnyagin, 2023

Поступила в редакцию 16.05.2023
Принята к публикации 06.06.2023

Для цитирования:

Solonin S.V., Koroy V.V., Portnyagin D.V. Fossil sharks from Albian and Cenomanian deposits of the Kursk Oblast (Russia) // Инновационные научные исследования. 2023. № 6-1(30). С. 57-76. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>